

IMPROVEMENT OF CROP AGROTECHNOLOGY IN KARAKALPAKSTAN DEPENDING ON WATER SUPPLY

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Abstract:The article describes the results of scientific research on the improvement of agricultural technology for the cultivation of agricultural crops based on water supply in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, located on the shores of the Aral Sea.

Key words: crop, agrotechnology, water, cultivation, Aral Sea, supply;

Introduction. In ensuring the security of the Food Program of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the development of agriculture, the proper use of available resources in the context of climate change and water scarcity on the Aral Sea, it is important to improve crop technology, soil fertility, cultivation technology. is an issue.

Due to the reduction of water-intensive crops in the country in recent years, it is important to replace these cotton fields with reduced hectares, to improve crop productivity and soil fertility technology to ensure grain independence and food security in saline soils. application to production is a more important task.

Despite the fact that a large part of the agricultural land of the Republic of Karakalpakstan is saline, has poor reclamation conditions, and water supply is somewhat complicated, in recent years, as a result of intensive economic reforms, positive results have been achieved. In recent years, the production of wheat in the country increased by 2.9 times, cotton by 1.6 times, rice by 3.4 times, potatoes by 1.9 times, vegetables by 3.5 times, melons and fruits by 2.1 times, grapes by 2.6 times, livestock products, including meat (live weight) by 121.8%, milk by 132.3% and eggs by 216.7%.

The purpose of the research. The main purpose of the research is to identify ways to ensure high yields of agricultural crops in the fields and

maintain a balance of soil fertility in the Republic of Karakalpakstan in the conditions of saline soil-extreme climate, climate change and water scarcity.

Location and method of research. Field experiments were carried out on moderately saline soils on the experimental plot of the Karakalpak Agricultural Research Institute in Chimbay district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and on the experimental farm of the Karakalpak station of the Institute of Cereals and Legumes of the Republic of Uzbekistan in Nukus district.

The research was conducted on the basis of the manual "Methods of conducting field experiments" (2007), adopted at UzPITI. The experiments were placed in three repetitions on the basis of systems, and the data on productivity were analyzed on the basis of B. Dospekhov's manual "Methodology of field experiment" (1979-1985).

The results of the study are based on scientific experiments on the current ecological situation in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, water scarcity, saline soils and global climate change. Depending on the supply, it was determined that it is expedient to plan and plant low-water crops such as millet, sesame, oats, sunflowers.

Depending on the type of plant, biology and other indicators, it takes 8-12 biomass from the ground per year. To compensate for this loss, the Republic of Karakalpakstan actively maintains 3:4 1: 2 and 1:3 1:2 crop rotation systems and maintains semi-rotten manure per hectare at the rate of 13-14 tons per hectare per year to maintain soil fertility and farming. we need to go. Due to non-compliance with these rules, the analysis of research and calculation statistics shows that the soils of the Republic of Karakalpakstan are low in nutrients, including humus, which has decreased by 3-4 points in the last 30-40 years. It dropped to 41.3 points.

Based on the above, one of the important issues in the Republic of Karakalpakstan is to study the technology of improving the efficiency of quality and high yields of crops and soil fertility by improving crop agrotechnology.

Analyzing the results of the conducted experiments, it is necessary to take joint measures to restore the previous state of soil fertility and to obtain the planned yield from agricultural crops.

Conclusions:

1. Given the water shortage and climate change in the South Aral Sea region, it is advisable to focus on the elements of crop agro-technologies in the national economy, depending on the water supply.

2. For systematic farming, it is advisable to plan depending on the water supply and plant low-water crops such as millet, sesame, corn, sunflower.

3. Taking into account the soil and water conditions of the republic, we need to develop animal husbandry by increasing the area of cereals, legumes, natural and cultural pastures, which have a positive impact on soil fertility and give the planned yield in saline soil conditions.

4. In order to maintain soil fertility and conduct farming in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, we need to carry out 3: 4: 1: 2 and 1: 3: 1: 2 crop rotation systems and active fertilization of fields at the rate of 13-14 tons per hectare per year.

5. In order to maintain and increase soil fertility, we need to intensify crop rotation and fertilizer use on the farm, while at the same time planting mixed, intermediate and siderate crops.

6. It is economically proven that the transition of the form of management in the country from the form of farmers and other land users to the form of livestock-farmers gives high results.

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